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ISSUES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC AGRICULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON THE “GREEN ECONOMY”

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Abstract. This article examines the socio-economic issues surrounding the formation and development of organic agriculture in the context of the transition to a green economy. It presents, on a scientific basis, priority areas for addressing existing problems, as well as conclusions and recommendations on these issues.

Keywords: organic net product, gigagram, humus, compost, agroforestry, greenhouse effect, organic certification.

Introduction

Agriculture is one of the leading sectors of Uzbekistan’s economy, and the need to develop it based on a “green economy” is in line with global development trends. Specifically, more than 17 million of the country’s residents (over 50% of the total population) live in rural areas (2022). The country has a high birth rate (23.3 per thousand) and, consequently, a surplus of labor in rural areas. People under the age of 25 accounted for 45.5% of the population, and those under 30 accounted for more than 55%. Currently, over 20 million hectares are used for agriculture, including 3.2 million hectares of irrigated arable land, to grow food for the population and raw materials for various economic sectors. Therefore, the transition to a green economy is a pressing issue for our Republic.

The main purpose of this article is not only to examine the environmental challenges currently facing our Republic, but also-based on data regarding the state of

the environment and population growth-to propose scientifically sound solutions to these problems.

Literature Review on the Research Topic

In the course of research on this topic, a vast body of literature was carefully studied and analyzed, particularly the resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of our Republic, which set forth objectives for addressing existing environmental problems, the need to transition to organic agriculture, and ensuring its further development. Particular attention is drawn to specific publications on this issue by scholars from CIS countries and Uzbekistan.

In his article “International Experience in Implementing the ‘Green Economy’ Concept and Opportunities for Its Application in Uzbekistan,” Professor A.V. Vakhobov proposes a series of measures to address existing environmental problems in our Republic, measures that have been implemented in other countries, such as South Korea. And in the article “Problems of Agricultural Development Based on the ‘Green Economy,’” he proposes scientifically grounded measures regarding the need to establish organic agriculture in Uzbekistan. Russian scientists O. Romanova, Nikolaenko A., in “Summary of a Basic Analysis of the Situation in the Field of Landscape Restoration in the Aral Sea Basin on the Territory of the Republics of Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan,” propose a series of measures for the afforestation of the Aral Sea bed to stabilize the saline soil with perennial grasses and large shrubby trees.

Methodology

This article is based on comparative and economic-statistical methods of analysis. In addition, the research utilized methods of observation, data collection, analysis and synthesis, grouping, comparative analysis, case study, and a systems approach.

Analysis and Results

The Republic's high population growth rates since the 1960s and 1970s, the reclassification of agricultural land in the 1990s, and, in particular, the intensifying impact of global climate change during this period have created a number of challenges in the agricultural sector. Thus, over the past 20 years, the area of irrigated land per capita has decreased by 24 percent (from 0.23 to 0.16 hectares), and the average annual water supply has fallen from 3,048 to 158.9 cubic meters. According to forecasts, the area of irrigated land could shrink by another 20–25 percent over the next 30 years [3].

As a result of the inefficient use of agricultural land over many years, natural soil fertility and crop yields are declining, the quality of agricultural products is deteriorating, and environmental pollution is increasing.

Specifically, the content of available phosphorus in 93 percent of the soils of irrigated agricultural lands, exchangeable potassium in 68.3 percent, and humus (organic matter) in 79.3 percent has fallen below average.

Average annual water consumption in agriculture remains high at 45,696 million cubic meters, or 90 percent of the water resources consumed across all economic sectors.

Specifically, while in developed countries \$4–6 worth of agricultural output is produced per cubic meter of water, in our country this figure stands at \$0.15. According to a forecast by the World Resources Institute, by 2040 Uzbekistan will be among the 33 countries with the highest water scarcity [4]. The lack of a mechanism to cover the costs of delivering water for agricultural needs hinders the widespread adoption of water-saving technologies.

Declining crop yields have serious negative consequences for food security and the balance of payments, which underscores the need for sustainable water resource

management and the use of water-saving technologies in crop cultivation. Decree No. PP-4477 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 4, 2019 “On the Approval of the Strategy for the Transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a ‘Green’ Economy for the Period 2019–2030”, the goal was set to reduce water consumption for irrigation per hectare by 20 percent by 2030 (see Table 1).

Targets for agricultural development, in accordance with the Republic of Uzbekistan’s Strategy for 2020–2030 (see Table 1).

Table 1

Targets for agricultural development, in accordance with the Republic of Uzbekistan’s Strategy for 2020–2030

Targets for the implementation of agricultural development, in accordance with the Republic of Uzbekistan’s strategy for 2020–2030.	Background 2018	2021 y.	2025 y.	2030 y.
Percentage of the population that is undernourished.	6,3	5,0	3,0	0,0
Reduction in greenhouse gas emissions in agriculture by 2016 (in percent)	15,740 gigagrams* (2016)	10	30	50
Percentage increase in the number of farmers who apply optimal agricultural and environmental practices and have implemented an international quality management system	2	5	10	15
Percentage increase in the area of irrigated agricultural land where water-saving technologies have been implemented	1,7	10	20	32

Decrease in the proportion of highly saline land, in %	45	43	41	37
Increase in forested area, as a percentage, by 2018	3.2 million hectares	20	25	30
Growth in the area planted with tree nuts (pistachios, walnuts, almonds), as a percentage compared to 2018	11,634 hectares	10	15	18
Increase in government spending on agricultural research (as a percentage of gross agricultural output) compared to 2018	0,02	0,05	0,5	1,0

Source: Targets for agricultural development, in accordance with the Republic of Uzbekistan’s strategy for 2020–2030.

A **gigagram (Gg)** is a unit of mass equal to 10^9 grams, used in scientific research, including for measuring atmospheric emissions.

One of the priority areas identified in the “Strategy for the Development of Agriculture in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020–2030” is “...improving the system for the rational use of natural resources and environmental protection, which provides for the rational use of land, water, and forest resources.” This strategy sets out objectives such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions in agriculture by 50 percent by 2030 compared to 2016 levels, expanding the area of irrigated agricultural land by 32 percent through the adoption of water-saving technologies, and increasing forested areas by 30 percent.

Given the current conditions in our republic, the future development of agriculture can only be achieved through the adoption of organic farming methods. Organic agriculture is understood as a comprehensive system for managing agricultural production that promotes the conservation and development of the environment and the accumulation of natural capital. This system requires, first and foremost, the use of management mechanisms adapted to the region, rather than

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external resources, taking into account the specific conditions of each region. This implies the use of extensive methods in agricultural production, as well as agronomic, biological, and mechanical methods, where the use of synthetic materials is avoided.

Modern organic agriculture will develop based on a scientific approach. Crop production, soil science, feed production, animal husbandry, and other areas require advancement through the application of advanced “green technologies.” The principles of organic farming were developed in 1980 by the International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements and consist of health, ecology, justice, and care. Organic farming is developing in 181 countries around the world as an important component of the global “green economy.”

In the coming decades, a shortage of water for agriculture will become a problem. Agricultural development requires a great deal of water, and the transition to intensive agriculture requires even more. In the long term, increased agricultural productivity cannot be achieved through a proportional increase in water consumption. Global experience shows that agriculture requires the use of water-efficient methods. According to some estimates, 1 m³ of clean water increases crop yields by 50–80%. To reduce freshwater consumption in agriculture, it is advisable to use highly efficient irrigation technologies, collect rainwater through drainage, treat industrial wastewater, and reuse it.

According to a forecast by the World Resources Institute, by 2040 Uzbekistan will be among the 33 countries with the most severe water shortages. Declining crop yields have serious negative consequences for food security and the balance of payments, which necessitates sustainable water resource management and the use of resource-efficient high technologies in crop cultivation.

The only way to address the water shortage in our country is through reforestation. In particular, the development of agroforestry plays a vital role in

restoring degraded lands. Agroforestry promotes the balanced development of forestry and agriculture with the aim of improving soil quality. Trees capture greenhouse gases, produce oxygen, store rainwater, prevent soil erosion, and provide natural fertilizers for humus formation. To this end, the widespread use of tree leaves as organic fertilizer is highly effective. Increasing the amount of forests and woodlands not only helps preserve soil moisture but also leads to soil expansion and development, changes in the regional climate, and an increase in water resources.

Among the deciduous trees commonly found in our country, the mulberry tree and all its varieties rank second only to Russian poplars in terms of air purification, carbon dioxide absorption, and oxygen release. Expanding mulberry forests could have significant ecological benefits, providing substantial benefits in land conservation and silkworm cocoon production[8].

Most developed and developing countries around the world have certification systems for organic production. This system includes requirements for the processing, packaging, and storage of organic products, in addition to their production. An organic certificate is a document confirming that a company complies with organic requirements during the cultivation, production, packaging, and transportation of products. To obtain organic certification, a company must undergo an inspection by independent experts to verify compliance with organic production principles.

To obtain organic certification, a farm engaged in crop production, livestock farming, and product manufacturing must adhere to the following principles:

- 95% of the ingredients in the product must meet organic standards, while the remaining 5% must be natural and comply with EU requirements;

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- Land designated for organic production must be free of chemical fertilizers, pesticides, and other additives not permitted in organic farming for at least three years. The purity of the land is subject to regular laboratory testing;

- In livestock farming, all animals must be able to graze and move about freely. To prevent disease, it is prohibited to create conditions unsuitable for any species, or to use hormones or various antibiotics.

- At least 60% of the feed for grazing animals must be produced on the farm's own land, and if this is not possible, on another farm within the same area. Young animals must be fed their mother's milk for up to three months[4].

- Increasing mulberry groves when establishing agroforestry systems and planting them in multiple rows when clearing large tracts of land;

- When establishing forests, the number of fast-growing trees with strong wood and fruit trees (apricot, walnut, almond) should also be increased[8];

- Organizing and implementing effective irrigation technologies during the forest establishment process over an 8- to 10-year period.

In accordance with the Republic of Uzbekistan's Strategy for the Transition to a "Green Economy" in the Agricultural Sector by 2030, the following objectives are planned to be achieved:

- restoring pastures that have been taken out of production and implementing mechanisms for sustainable pasture management;

- adopting organic farming methods[4];

- crop rotation to ensure continuous ground cover on arable land and natural nutrient cycling;

- Attracting investment in production and processing (green), as well as creating value chains for agricultural and food products;

- Proper storage and processing of organic livestock waste;

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- Preventing the contamination of water sources by agricultural waste;
- Breeding high-yielding livestock breeds and plant varieties that are resistant to salinization, drought, and other hazardous phenomena and threats; preserving the gene pool of local livestock breeds and plant varieties, as well as the gene pool of the wild ancestors of cultivated plants.

- Reducing water losses in agriculture by 10%;
- Reducing water consumption in agriculture by 15% (per hectare);
- Increasing wastewater treatment efficiency to 80% [2];

In our opinion, the following tasks must also be implemented:

- One of the objectives set forth in the plan is to diversify the composition of the orchards; that is, as the planting of perennial trees expands, it is advisable to plant all varieties of mulberry and apricot trees alongside hardy fruit and ornamental trees to increase the production of silkworm cocoons and apricots. As we know, dried apricots are produced from apricots, which are in demand not only in the CIS countries but also worldwide.

- As the cultivation of perennial grasses expands, it is advisable to increase clover sowing, as it enriches the soil with nitrogen;

- Increasing the total forest area on the dried-up bed of the Aral Sea in Uzbekistan to 60 percent and planting heat-loving turangul and karagach (gudzhum) trees, as well as large wild shrubby trees such as jida, which grow even on saline soils, at a distance of 3 meters apart between rows of 10- to 12-year-old saxaul trees;

- Organize the planting of hardy hawthorn and other heat-loving trees at close intervals (1.5 x 2 m) between large shrubby trees (saxaul, wild jujube) and water them for 8–10 years (after which the trees will grow by retaining moisture on their own).

- When organizing forestry, it is necessary to take into account that broad-leaved trees with strong wood that grow in the central regions of Russia and Ukraine (ash, sharp-leaved maple, oak, linden, aspen, and Tatar maple) thrive very well under the climatic conditions of our country, especially in the central regions. However, they must be irrigated to maintain soil moisture for 8–10 years and planted at close intervals of 3×3 m.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Although organic farming exists in Uzbekistan, scientific criteria for classifying products grown using this method on specific grounds have not been sufficiently developed. Despite the availability of organic agricultural products, there are no established norms or standards confirming their environmental purity. Therefore, based on international practice, it is necessary to develop a legal framework for the implementation of standards for organic products, as well as systems for their regulation and certification.

In Uzbekistan, the establishment and development of agroforestry systems and the afforestation of cultivated lands—based on the principles of the “green economy” and aimed at preventing soil erosion and degradation—could bear fruit in the coming decades and help alleviate the water shortage to some extent.

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